

A Simple Method of Determination of Transport Number of Ions

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A simple apparatus and method for determination of transport number for Na_2SO_4 and K_2SO_4 , based on measurement of the sulphate ion transported by the current as determined by direct titration of the anolyte before and after electrolysis is described. The method is suitable for routine use by students.

THERE are two methods viz, moving boundary method and Hittorf method for the determination of transport number. The former is a research tool rather difficult for student use. The latter can be used successfully only in some special cases (such as Ag^+ in AgNO_3), particularly for dissolving electrodes to avoid disturbance due to gas liberation. That Hittorf method in general gives unreliable result unless special precautions are taken is well known. Palit pointed out¹ that this is due to the hitherto unnoticed fact that ion depletion in the intermediate zone takes place whenever the cell has more than one bend. We describe here a simple method of determination of transport number of ions present in alkali metal sulphates and similar salts using a very simple apparatus suitable for routine student use.

Apparatus: The cell is a W-tube¹ (Fig. 1) of a total capacity of about 120 ml and the electrodes are bright platinum wires. This cell design (W-tube) has the advantages of preventing the intermixing of the anode and the cathode solutions through diffusion and convection (thermal or mechanical) during electrolysis and of easy separation of the anolyte and the catholyte.

Theory: From the very definition of transport number (t), it is clear that if Na_2SO_4 solution is the electrolyte and current is exclusively carried by Na^+ and SO_4^{2-} ions, the number of equivalents of SO_4^{2-} ions (or Na^+ ions) which have crossed any imaginary line at the centre divided by the total current equivalent, is the respective transport number (t). However, some H^+ and OH^- ions may also migrate and complicate the above simple picture. This is easily avoided by adding acid and alkali at the cathode and anode respectively in a slightly over the theoretical amount at the start of the experiment. This would not affect the migration of the sulphate ions, which we have chosen to measure. We therefore have

$$t = \frac{\text{Equivalent of the ion migrated to anode (or cathode) as a results of electrolysis}}{\text{Total current equivalent (Q)}} \dots (1)$$

Fig. 1. Apparatus (W-tube) for measuring transport number.

Procedure: The W-tube is filled up with the electrolyte, K_2SO_4 or Na_2SO_4 (0.1 N), solution as shown in Fig. 1 so that the solution levels at the two side limbs are always somewhat below that of P. This can be achieved by filling the W-tube with electrolyte up to the level P, then pipetting out the solution from the side limbs after closing the stop cock P. Before starting the current, calculated amount (on the basis of 1 mA-hour = 0.0373 m equiv of acid/alkali) of $\text{N H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and N KOH , which is enough to neutralise the alkali and acid produced at cathode and anode, is added carefully at the respective electrodes. Electrolysis is then immediately carried out between the two Pt-electrodes. Current is adjusted to 50 to 80 mA using a regulated power supply (75-100 volts). A

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coulometer is included in series as an additional check for Q. After about 1 hr the electrolysis is allowed to stop. By carefully opening the stop cock P at the middle of the W-tube the anode solution gets separated from the cathodic solution. Total volume of anode solution is noted. Taking 20 ml of anodic solution, its total sulphate concentration is estimated² several times volumetrically using 0.2 N BaCl₂ and Na-rhodizonate indicator. Mean value is taken for calculation. The same procedure is carried out for the estimation of sulphate content of the original solution before electrolysis. Now, from the net gain of SO₄²⁻ content at anode chamber after electrolysis, the transport number of SO₄²⁻ ion is easily calculated. Some results are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF TRANSPORT NO. OF SO₄²⁻ IN K₂SO₄

Electrolyte : (0.1 N) K ₂ SO ₄ Temperature : 25°			
Current and time in meq Q	Initial conc. of SO ₄ ²⁻ C ₁ meq	Final conc. of SO ₄ ²⁻ C ₂ meq	t = (C ₂ - C ₁)/Q
1.865	5.906	6.878	0.518
2.020	5.316	6.878	0.528
2.787	5.588	7.042	0.522
2.980	5.142	6.659	0.509
3.021	5.697	7.218	0.528
3.120	5.028	6.678	0.528
3.180	5.338	7.021	0.531
			Mean 0.522

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF TRANSPORT NO. OF Na⁺ IN Na₂SO₄

Electrolyte : (0.1 N) Na ₂ SO ₄ Temperature : 25°			
Current and time in meq Q	Initial conc. of Na ⁺ C ₁ meq	Final conc. of Na ⁺ C ₂ meq	t = (C ₂ - C ₁)/Q
1.865	5.530	6.258	0.390
3.104	5.429	6.679	0.403
3.104	5.429	6.908	0.397
			Mean 0.397

We have applied similar procedure for determination of transport number of Na⁺ ion by direct titration² of the increase of Na⁺ ion concentration at the cathode as a result of electrolysis. Here also the corresponding acid and alkali are pre-added to the cathode and the anode, respectively. Some results are included in Table 1. Our values agree within a few per cent with the values reported in the literature (t_{Na⁺} in Na₂SO₄ = 0.386 and t_{SO₄²⁻} = 0.521 in K₂SO₄).

References

1. S. R. PALIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **50**, 968.
2. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis".